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Research Article

MOTIVES TO CHOOSE MEDICINE AS A PROFESSIONQudsia Umaira Khan, Aimen Malik, Umme Farwa, Farida Hafeez, Hunniya Bint e Riaz
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Abstract:

Background: One of the most important and major decision in life is to choose a profession. This decision is of foremost importance as it affects your future life. Among various professions and educational fields, doctors are ranked among the top most and are also known as the cream of society. The decision to seek admission in medicine is one of the foremost important tasks and is also significant career selections to be made by a physician.

Aim: To discuss different motives, why students choose medicine as a profession.

Methodology: This comparative cross sectional study was conducted at CMH Lahore medical college during the year 2017-2018 using a self-administered questionnaire. It was distributed to 100 first year medical students in the college. Data was collected and analyzed by SPSS. A standardized questionnaire was designed for the cohort study and the demographics assessed the age and gender of the participants. The paper questionnaires were handed out to all the 1st year students, at the beginning of a compulsory lecture.

Result: The most common reason overall for selecting medicine as a profession was an interest in medical field (19%) and this was also the most common reason among the male students (26.3%) while recognition as respectable citizen (18%) was the second most common reason among both male and female students. A willingness to help patients (16%) was significantly more common among female students ($p < 0.0025$) compared to the male students. Students who accepted that they could not find anything better to do (13%).

Conclusion: Students opt for medical profession for the sake of respect and interest in medical field.

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INTRODUCTION:

During the last two decades in the South Asian countries, various financial, social and political changes have had a huge influence on every field of life. This includes people's morals, ambitions and even their career selections.(1)

One of the most important and major decision in life is to choose a profession. This decision is of foremost importance as it affects your future life. There is always some ambition behind this and it helps them to spend a satisfying career.(2)

Among various professions and educational fields, doctors are ranked among the top most and are also known as the cream of society (3). This inclines most of the students to choose medicine as their career after completion of their secondary schooling considering it a prestigious profession(4). It has been observed that students are fascinated to become doctor during their initial years of education and two of the most prominent reasons behind are financial stability and social pressure(5). The decision to seek admission in medicine is one of the foremost important tasks and is also significant career selections to be made by a physician.

The decision to join the field of medicine is basically established on the aptitude of oneself, the regard, reverence, influence of the family and a service to mankind. To get economically strong is not a considerable reason so far. It is found that many students do not get proper career counseling and opt for this career due to family influence. In this regard, concise discussion and career counseling is necessary for making a complement decision. The students should be encouraged to choose a profession that suits their aptitude so that they can contribute better to the profession. The merit kept for the disproportional recruitment of students having socio – economic benefits seems to be a sign of dormancy. When the comparison for reflection between the genders is made, stats showed that a considerable difference exist as per their respective vocational profession and personal background. The pre-medical schools schemes are the main cause of escalating ways of enticing the students to select medical profession.

METHODOLOGY:

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted at CMH Lahore medical college during the year 2017-2018 using a self-administered questionnaire. It was distributed to 100 first year medical students in the college. Data was collected and analyzed by SPSS. The literature search was carried out independently in PubMed, Google Scholar and NCBI databases for articles published from year 2006 till 2018. The research primarily focused 1st year medical students studying at Combined Military Hospital Lahore Medical College. Ethical approval was received from the Ethics Department of CMH LMC. All the respondents voluntarily participated after having the purpose of the study explained to them. A consent form was attached to each questionnaire while all the results were kept anonymous and confidential. A standardized questionnaire was designed for the cohort study and the demographics assessed the age and gender of the participants. The paper questionnaires were handed out to all the 1st year students, at the beginning of a compulsory lecture. Attempts were made to keep questions as similar as possible to the published methodology; however some minor adjustments were required in accordance with the psychosocial model of Pakistan. After a brief introduction of the project and instructions about filling out the questionnaire, participants were first asked to choose the statement that most accurately represented their current position with regards to their future career. In order to assess motivation they were presented with a number of factors. Ample amount of time was given to the participants to make their choices after which the forms were collected and analyzed.

RESULTS:

The most common reason overall for selecting medicine as a profession was an interest in medical field (19%) and this was also the most common reason among the male students (26.3%) while recognition as respectable citizen (18%) was the second most common reason among both male and female students. A willingness to help patients (16%) was significantly more common among female students ($p < 0.0025$) compared to the male students. However probably the most surprising outcome was the overall percentage of students who accepted that they could not find anything better to do (13%).

DISCUSSION:

Doctors are in charge of taking care, giving attention to his problems, how minor the issue be. They assess sign and symptoms, ponder potential diagnoses, carry out examinations and investigations, recommend patients on treatment choices and observe the

improvement of the condition and response of treatment. (RBritish Medical Association)

Motivation is defined as the process that triggers a strong desire, pledge, escorts, and sustains a continuous effort towards goal. It comprises the

genetic, passionate, social, and rational, and intellectual forces that motivate performance (6)

According to WORLD HEALTH REPORT 2006, it is estimated that over the period of next 10 years there can be shortage of approximately 4.3 million doctors. Hence globally a disaster in work force for health is estimated worldwide.(7) In underdeveloped countries where the income is low, there is more shortage of medical professionals. They tend to migrate to the countries which are more rewarding and the chances to prosper are more. Therefore, in middle- and low-income countries, the shortage of trained health personnel was exacerbated by the migration to high income countries.(8)

A study done by Teppo J. Heikkilä showed that "Interest in people" was the major objective for opting medicine as a career .(4)

From various earlier investigations, the data indicate that medical students drive views and values around their studies and future profession have an influence on the enthusiasm to take the training program and on the knowledge, academic presentation as well as on the selections made for upcoming career alleyways.(1)

In the second half of 20th century and the 21st century, noteworthy development has been made in the implementation of equivalence in gender, specifically in regards to job opportunities and employment. Field of medicine is one of the most prominent fields. (2015 Staff Care 5)

A systematic literature review earlier done by [Sonu Goel](#),[Federica Angeli](#),[Nonita Dhirar](#), also explained that the chief motivating issues that arose were specifically because of the scientific curiosity in medical profession, (5) ,keenness to know , community interest and desire to help humanity. A survey carried by Lambrou and Kontodimopoulos ND showed that the sense of accomplishment , satisfaction and achievements can be considered as the foremost reason for motivation and was ranked first among the four main motivators, followed by salary or income considerations, co-workers and profession aspects(10)

Analysis of career selection traditionally is at two extremes having great differences .One is demographic difference i.e. gender, social status and family at one extreme and is firm and difficult to change. Similarly personality also matters to a great deal and is found to be firm, however other measures such as learning styles empathy varies from person to

person (9). The socio economic factors and status also has a great influence on profession selection.(11)

The choice of career selection has got more complicated because of the fact that people are more dependent on mass media. It has been proven that the people of 21st century are more vulnerable to media, so the society due to the high exposure and media ruling people's profession are more affecting them. Statics showed that there are various factors as competitive scarcity of specialists and the variety of patients are more common among male students and factors sympathy, and teaching facilities were concerned with female students

CONCLUSION:

More efforts should be spend to improve the assistances available to Pakistani students in selecting their profession. Students opt for medical profession for the sake of respect and interest in medical field.

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